

Studies on Potential Pesticides: Part. I. Synthesis of N-phthalimidoacetyl-N'-arylureas and Corresponding Thioureas

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Received 29 January 1972

The insecticidal and acaricidal properties of O, O-dimethyl S-phthalimido methyl phosphorodithioate has been reported recently¹. It controls codling moth and suppresses spider mites. The activity of similar compounds with phthalimido group has been reported by Tolkmith², and Martin³. The insecticidal, rodenticidal and fungicidal properties of chloro acetylarylureas have been reported by Hoegberg *et al.*⁴ Sen Gupta *et al.*⁵ have reported various esters of N-chloroacetylureas as anticholinesterase and thus they possess insecticidal activity. Dieke⁶ suggested that acute toxicity of thioureas is enhanced when single aromatic radical is attached to one of the N atom. Keeping these facts in view several substituted ureas and thioureas with phthalimido group has been synthesised by condensing phthalylglycylchloride and ureas in order to study the effect of various substituents on the insecticidal activity.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected.

Preparation of N-phthalimidoacetyl-N'-arylureas : Phthalylglycylchloride⁷ (0.01 mole) and the appropriate arylureas^{8,9} (0.01 mole) were dissolved in 40 ml of dry benzene and was refluxed under anhydrous conditions on water bath for 5 hr. The benzene was removed under reduced pressure and the crude solid was washed with cold water and recrystallised from ethanol.

The m.p., and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Preparation of N-phthalimidoacetyl-N'-arylthioureas : Phthalylglycylchloride (0.01 mole) was taken in dry acetone in a three necked flask equipped with a reflux condenser, a dropping funnel and mechanical stirrer. Ammonium thiocyanate in 10 ml of dry acetone was added dropwise to the above solution under constant stirring. After the complete addition of the ammonium thiocyanate solution the mixture was refluxed for 15 mins. At the end of the period heating was stopped to moderate the reaction, then a solution of 0.01 mole of appropriate arylamine in dry acetone was introduced dropwise. After standing for 5 hours the mixture was poured carefully into the crushed ice. The precipitated product was filtered, washed with cold water several times and recrystallised from a suitable solvent.

TABLE 1

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analytical Data	
					%N found	calculated
1.	Phenyl	225	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄	12.71	13.00
2.	<i>o</i> -tolyl	206	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	12.16	12.46
3.	<i>m</i> -tolyl	222	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	11.96	12.46
4.	<i>p</i> -tolyl	220	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄	12.32	12.46
5.	<i>p</i> -anisyl	218	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅	11.78	11.89
6.	<i>o</i> -phenetyl	205	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.32	11.44
7.	<i>p</i> -phenetyl	220	65	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅	11.26	11.44
8.	<i>p</i> -chloro phenyl	210	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₄ Cl	11.62	11.73
9.	Cyclohexyl	215	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄	12.56	12.80

The m.p. yield and analytical data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical Data%		
					found	calculated	
1.	Phenyl	190	76	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ S	N	11.96	12.39
					S	9.36	9.44
2.	2 methyl-phenyl	212	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	N	11.82	11.90
					S	9.21	9.06
3.	4 methyl-phenyl	205	68	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S	N	11.73	11.90
					S	9.92	9.06
4.	2 methoxy-phenyl	214	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	N	11.27	11.38
					S	8.92	8.67
5.	4 methoxy-phenyl	190	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ S	N	11.18	11.38
					S	9.06	8.67
6.	2 ethoxy-phenyl	180	68	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₄ S	N	10.87	10.96
					S	8.39	8.36
7.	<i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl	212	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ SCl	N	11.32	11.26
					S	8.26	8.58
8.	<i>m</i> -nitro-phenyl	208	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅ S	N	14.32	14.58
					S	8.68	8.33
9.	<i>p</i> -nitro-phenyl	232	54	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅ S	N	14.64	14.58
					S	8.52	8.33

The insecticidal activity of these compounds will be communicated later on as it is under investigation.

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Head of the Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow for providing laboratory facilities and grateful acknowledgment is made to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for providing a junior research fellowship to A.K.R.

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